

REVIEW ON POLYHERBAL ANTIDANDRUFF SHAMPOO

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ABSTRACT

The present study is based upon the review Poly-herbal Antidandruff Shampoo. The Dried Herbal Ingredients includes, Fenugreek, Hibiscus flowers, Orange peel, Rose petals, Chamomile petals, Eucalyptus leaves, Flax seeds, Ginger powder, Bengal gram, Amla, Reetha, Shikakai were studied by based on the literature review. Hence, we have concluded that the above ingredients having following therapeutic & prophylactic activities like Anti-Dandruff, Anti-bacterial, Anti-viral, Anti-fungal, Nourishing, Smoothing Scalp irritation, Hair growing, Hair strengthening effect & reduces Microbial Growth, Further investigations on different activities have to be done.

KEYWORD: Smoothing Scalp Irritation, Poly Herbal Anti-Dandruff, Nourishing, Dried Herbal Ingredients, Microbial

Growth.

INTRODUCTION

Shampoos are most widely used cosmetic products for cleansing hair & scalp in our daily life. A shampoo is basically a solution of detergent containing suitable additive for another benefits such as hair conditioning enhancement, lubrications, medications. Now adays somany synthetic herbal medicated and non medicated shampoos are available in the market, but the popularity of herbal shampoos among consumer is on raise because of their natural

origin, safe to use free from side effects. The present attempt is based on the herbal raw materials without using synthetic materials.

HERBAL INGREDIENTS USED IN ANTIDANDRUFF HERBAL SHAMPOO

MATERIALS

Collection of Materials: The various herbal sources of Materials were collected from the medicinal garden, purchased from local super market & surroundings of Dhanvanthari Institute of Pharmaceutical sciences.

S.no	Name of the Compound	Scientific name	Pictures	Genus	uses
01	Fenugreek	Trigonella foenum graecum		Trigonella	Manage blood sugar levels, promotes breast milk production in lactating women, hormonal balance, hair care, itchiness.
02	Hibiscus flowers	Hibiscus rosa-sinensis		Hibiscus l.	Hair treatment, skin hydration inhibit, aging reduces, stress relief immunity booster, cancer cell growth,.
03	Chamomile petals	Matricaria chamomilla		Matricaria	Relieves anxiety & stress, insomnia, aromatherapy, anti-inflammatory, hair care, anti-microbial and cosmetics.
04	Eucalyptus leaves	Eucalyptus globulus		Eucalyptus	Anti-microbial, anti-septic, sleep-aid, anti-septic and anti-inflammatory properties.
05	Orange peel	Citrus Sinesis		Citrus	Stress relief, skin care, anti-microbial and anti-fungal. Antiinflammatory, skin brightening, Relieves acne dark spots

06	Ginger powder	Zingiber officinale		Zingiber	Nausea relief, Digestive aid, Reduces pain & inflammation, Relieves cardiac diseases, Aromatherapy.
07	Bengal gram	Cicer arietinum		Cicer	Dietary fiber, weight management reduces blood sugar levels controls anxiety and stress.
08	Rose petals	Rosa sinensis		Rosa	Smoothness, menstrual cramps, promotes skin health, improves mood.
09	Amla	Phyllanthus embilica		Phyllanthus	Immunity booster, promote radiant skin, strengthen hair, aids digestion, improves heart health
10	Reetha	Sapindus mukorossi		Sapindus	Treating dandruff, Natural shampoo, Hair growth & strength, prevents greying.
11	Shikakai	Acacia concinna		Acacia	Natural hair cleanser, conditioner, traditional medicine, rich in vitamins A,C,D.
12	Flax seeds	Linum usitatissimum		Linum	Digestive health, promote heart health, improve digestion, reduces hairfall, Balance hormones, Reduces cancer

01. Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum*)

Scientific name: *Trigonella foenum*

Order: -Fabales

Genus: - Trigonella

Family: - Fabaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: Carbohydrates (20-25), proteins (20-30), lipids (5-10)

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Alkaloids: The main component of trigonellene 0.2 to 0.38% along with smaller amounts of choline, gentianine, carpaine and onoline.

Steroidal saponins: it constitute 2 to 5% of seed and responsible for its bitter taste key sapogenins includes diosgenin, yamogenin, gitogenin and tigogenin.

Amino acids: It contains type ubigue free non protein amino acids 4-hydroxyisoleucine which has insulin stimulating properties.

Flavonoids & Polyphenols: Apigenin, luteolin, quercetin, orientin, vitexin, antioxidant benefit

Therapeutic uses

Lactation aid: Used to treat various as galactagogue stimulating mammary glands, to enhance breast milk production.

Hair care: Fenugreek used to treat dandruff, itchiness, and other scalp problems.

Cholesterol and heart health: studies indicate that can lower total cholesterol & serum lipid levels

02. Hibiscus flowers

Scientific name: Hibiscus rosa-sinensis

Order: - Malvales

Genus: - Hibiscus

Family: -Malvaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: Anthocyanins, minerals & vitamins, flavonoids, phenolics acids, organic acids.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Anthocyanins: These natural pigments give the flowers their deep red and purple colors major anthocyanins includes cyaniding 3-sophoroside, delphinidin3-sambubioside and cyanidin3- sambubioside acting as potent antioxidants.

Minerals: Calyces and leaves contain essential minerals including calcium iron and phosphorous.

vitamins: Hibiscus is a excellent source of vitaminc, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin and carotene.

Phytochemicals: Additional classess of compounds include saponins, tannins, mucilages, cyclopeptide alkaloids and bita sitosterol, which contribute to the modern pharmacological uses.

Organic acids: Hibiscus is renowned for plantacids, primarily citric acid, malic acid, tartaric acid, hibiscus acid hydroxyl citric acid lactone, which give the plant its tart flavour and beneficial properties.

Therapeutic uses

Promotes hair growth: Packed with amino acids and vitamin c it stimulates the blood circulation in the scalp and provide nutrients.

Reduces hair fall & prevent breakage: The plants natural mucilage acts as adeep conditioning agent smoothing hair cuticles and reinforcing the hair structure from root to tip.

Prevent premature greying: High in antioxidants and natural pigments, Regular use helps nourish hair & maintains your natural hair colour.

03. Chamomile petals

Scientificname: *Chamomile nobile*

Order: -Asterales

Genus: - Matricaria

Family: - Asteracace.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Chamomile contains over 120 seconadary metabolites flavonoids, essential oils, terpenoids and coumarins.

Active constituents

Terpenoids: These are volatile oils that provide aroma it includes chamazulene, bisalool and bisalool oxides (A&B)

Flavonoids: over 50 flavonoids have been identified have been identified in chamomile some of them are Apigenin luteolin, quercitin and rutin glycosides.

Coumarins: These are naturally occurring phenolics compounds contribute anti inflammatory and antispasmodic effects.

Therapeutic uses

Soothe scalp inflammation: It is rich in flavonoids which provides anti inflammatory effects.it is highly effective for relieving irritated scalp & itchy.

Antioxidant protection: - it gives protection from the uv exposure & pollution, generate free radical that prevent hair fiber from breakage and split ends.

Deep hydration and frizz control: by naturally locking in moisture chamomile hydrates dry brittle hair making it softer easier to detangle.

04. Eucalyptus leaves

Scientific name: *Eucalyptus globulus*

Order: Myrtales

Genus: Eucalyptus

Family: Myrtaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: cineole, monoterpenes polyphenolic flavonoids.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

inflammatory, 1,8-cineole monoterpenes Oxygenated monoterpenes sesquiterpenes, polyphenolic flavonoids.

Therapeutic uses

Relieves cold symp: It is widely used as a cold remedy due to its anti-inflammatory and muscle relieving properties.

Treats dry skin: Using eucalyptus may help in improve dry skin by increasing its ceramide content, ceramides are the type of fatty acid in your skin responsible for maintaining its barrier and retaining moisture.

May reduce pain: It inhaling eucalyptus essential oil may help decrease pain due to its anti inflammatory and analgesic compounds.

05. ORANGE PEEL

Scientific Name: *Citrus Aurantium dulcis*

Order: Sapindales

Genus: Citrus

Family: Rutaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Essential oils: 2-5%, Flavonoids: 1-3%, Limonoids: 1-2%, Carotenoids: 0.5 – 1.5%, Pectin: 10-20%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Hesperidin: A flavonoid with anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular / protective properties.

Limonin: A limonoid with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Limonene: A monoterpene with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Therapeutic uses

STRESS RELIEF: Orange peel has a calming effect on the mind and body, reducing stress and anxiety level.

SKIN CARE: Orange peel is used in skin care products due to its antiseptics and anti-fungal properties.

ANTI MICROBIAL: Orange peel has antimicrobial properties, which help to prevent the growth of macro-organisms, reducing risk of infections.

06. ROSE PETALS

Scientific name: *Rosa sinensis*

Order: - Rosales

Genus: -Rosa

Family: - Rosaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Essential oils: 1-3%, Flavanoids:5-10%, Phenolic acids:2-5%, Vitamins and minerals:1-5%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Geraniol: An essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Linalool: An essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and sedative properties.

Gallic acid: A phenolic acid with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Therapeutic uses

SOOTHENS MENSTRUAL CRAMPS: The powder may help ease menstrual cramps, blotting and other symptoms associated with PMS due to its anti-spasmodic and anti-inflammatory properties.

PROMOTES SKIN HEALTH: Rose petals powder may help to reduce inflammation, improve skin texture, and promote wounds healing due to its anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

IMPROVES MOOD: The powder may help alleviate symptoms of depression, improve mood, and promote relaxation due to its anti-depressant and anxiolytic properties.

07. GINGER

Scientific name: *Zingiber officinale*

Order: - zingiberales

Genus: -Zigiber

Family: - Zingiberaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: Essential pungent phenolics compounds, gingerols, shagerols, zingerone zingiberene, making with essential oils.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Pungent phenolic compounds: these compounds are primarily responsible for ginger signature spicy taste and potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant property.

Gingerols: The most abundant polyphenols found in fresh ginger such as, 8,10 gingerols.

Terpenes: These volatile compounds give ginger the distinct aromatic fragrance and provide antimicrobial and tumour-inhibiting properties.

Therapeutic uses

Nausea and vomiting: It is commonly used to ease morning sickness and is widely recognized as a safe non-pharmaceutical remedy.

Chemotherapy & post surgery : Ginger is often used to help manage post-operative and nausea caused by chemotherapy treatments.

Metabolic and cardiovascular health: It maintains in regulating blood sugar level and managing blood lipids. Acts as a vasodilator which can help promote healthy blood circulation and lower blood pressure.

08. Bengal gram

Scientific name: *Cicer arietinum*

Order: Fabales

Genus: Cicer

Family: Fabaaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

It consists of protein 17-22% carbohydrates 50-60% dietary fibre 17% fat 6% apart from this it also contains micronutrients & minerals.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Polyphenols & flavonoids: Rich in antioxidants like quercetin and kaempferol as well as phenolics acids ex caffeic acid.

Phytosterols & saponins: Plant sterols that help manage lipid profiles.

Alkaloids & Tannins: A found mostly in the seed coat contributing to antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.

Therapeutic uses

Metabolic and diabetic support: helps stabilize blood sugar and insulin levels due to its low glycemic index and high soluble fiber content.

Cardiovascular health: soluble fiber helps in lowering LDL cholesterol while maintaining HDL good cholesterol.

Anemia Management: rich in iron folate, which helps boost haemoglobin and transport oxygen effectively.

09. Amla

Scientific name: *Phyllanthus emblica*

Order: - Malpighiales

Genus: -phyllanthus

Family: - phyllanthaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Vitamin c, Flavanoids, polyphenols hydrolysable tannins and essential fatty acids

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Emblicanins A and B: these low molecular weight hydrolysable tannins are considered the most potent antioxidants in amla.

Vitamin C: Amla is one of the rich source of vit C it exists in bound form with other acids

Gallic acid and ellagic acid: These are prominent phenolic acid that significantly contribute to the fruits ability to scavenge free radicals and fight infections.

Therapeutic uses

Immunity and respiratory health: Its high vitamin C content boosts white blood cell production helping the body fight infections.

Digestion and Gut health: Amla stimulates digestive enzymes and act as a gentle laxative relieving constipation and soothing hyperacidity.

Heart & metabolic health: It helps in maintaining blood sugar level lower cholesterol and arterial plague.

10 REETHA

Scientific name: *Sapindus mukorosi*

Order: - Sapindales

Genus: - Sapindus

Family: Sapindaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: Essential sugars, mucilage, proteins, fatty acids.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Saapindosides (A-E): Major triterpenoid saponins responsible for the mild foaming and emulsifying action when mixed with water.

Mukuroziosides: Specialized glycosides contributing to the herbs surfactant and therapeutic properties.

Flavonoids: A powerful anti-oxidant that protect the scalp and skin from oxidative stress.

Therapeutic uses

Scalp cleansing: Acts as a mild, natural surfactant that removes dirt, excess oi and product buildup without stripping natural moisture.

Dandruff control: Antimicrobial and anti inflammatory properties soothe itchy scalpsand combat dandruff causing microbes.

Respiratory relief: Acts as natural expectorant to help clear mucus congestion in the lungs.

11. Shikakai

Scientific name: *Acacia concinna*

Order: Fabales

Genus: Acacia

Family: Fabaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Acacic acid, pentacyclic triterpenoid saponins, flavonoids, phytosterols & terpenoids, tannins alkaloids.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Saponins : Act as a natural detergents(foaming agents)that gently cleanse the scalp by binding to dirt and excess sebum without stripping natural protective oils.

Acacic acid & lactone: An triterpenoidal comounds that provide foundational cleansing and anti-inflammatory properties.

Flavonoids: Rutin and quercetin act as powerful antioxidants that shield hair follicles from oxidative stress and environmental damage.

Therapeutic uses

Hair cleanser: It acts as a natural hair cleanser. Acts as a mild, natural surfactant that removes dirt, excess oi and product buildup without stripping natural moisture.

Antidandruff: Antimicrobial and anti inflammatory properties soothe itchy scalpsand combat dandruff causing microbes.

Wound healing & skin disorders: Shikakai powder may help to reduce inflammation, improve skin texture, and promote wounds healing due to its anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

12. Flax seeds

Scientific name: *linum usitatissimum*

Order: - Malpighiales

Genus: linum

Family: - linaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Acacic acid, flax seeds consists of 32-35% lipids, fats 20-25%, proteins 20-28%,dietary fiber and minor amounts of moisture & ash values.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Alpha linolenic acid :this essential poly unsaturated omega 3 fatty acid accounts for about 50-60%. of flax seeds total lipid content.it is highly valued for reducing inflammation& supporting heart health and lowering the risk of cardio vascular diseases.

lignans :An flaxseed is the richest known dietary source of phytoestrogens.

Soluble fiber: the mucilage in flax seeds primarily composed of arabinoxylon and rhamnogalacturoman slows digestion, regulates blood sugar and helps lower bad LDL cholesterol.

Therapeutic uses

Digestive Health: It acts as a bulk forming laxative high mucilage and dietary fiber contents absorb water increasing stool bulk and earning bowel movement.

Heart health: Helps to lower total LDL cholesterol levels and regulates blood pressure omega-3- alfa linolenic acid reduces the arterial inflammation & supports cardiovascular function

Cancer supports: Lignans & antioxidants possess inflammatory properties that are research for their potential to reduce the risk of Hormone sensitive cancer such as breast & prostate cancer.

CONCLUSION

In the present scenario, people need cure for certain hair problems without any side effects. Herbal ingredients opened the way to formulate without any side effects. Anti dandruff Herbal shampoos are considered as sustaining and protective way to advance the appearance of hair & removing of dandruff. Thus, in the present work, it is very good attempt to formulate the herbal shampoo containing naturally available ingredients like chamomile, Hibiscus, orangepeel, fenugreek, ginger, Bengal gram, shikakai, reetha, flax seeds, Eucalyptus, Rose petals, Amla. It is suggested that the prepared formulation was physically and microbiologically stable and possesses characteristics of Antidandruff formulation for hair care.

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